

Cloud Computing Technology Helps India to Become Information Atmanirbhar (Self-Depend): A Review

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Abstract: -Present Article is focused on recent concept cloud computing technology application in information centre or library for making Information Atmanirbhar Bharat. Method of the study is review of past studies related to cloud computing technology from books, journals, conference proceeding and internet. The study covered concept of cloud computing technology, its types, and application in information centre or library for making information atmanirbhar Bharat. The cloud computing technology has brought revolutionary changes in information and library profession.

Keywords: -Cloud Computing, Information Atmanirbhar Bharat, Information self -depend India, ICT.

1.1 Introduction:-Before the emerging of computer technology and internet, information centres or libraries were provided and fulfilled their own user's needs of information. That time, while providing information services to the users, information centres were faced limitations of location, time and lack of enough financial availability. Computer technology enables information centres or libraries to work collaborative manner as information resources sharing, information centre's networking and consortia for providing information resources to the users. Information communication technology has changed scenario of limitations of information centres and libraries by providing information sources. In the recent trend and technology, information centres or libraries are adopting cloud computing for supplying seamless services with quality in a cost effective and economic way. In the Information era, cloud computing brought revolutionary changes in information technology after computer and internet revolution. Cloud computing technology is emerged as a boom for information centres or libraries. Cloud computing offers various opportunities to connect information services with information cloud. It is advance technology in distributed computing, parallel computing and grid computing. Cloud computing is available on pay per use real time service on the internet. Present study reviews the concept of cloud computing, its importance, types and application in information centres or libraries for becoming self-depend or atmanirbhar of information in India.

1.2 Literature Reviews:

Cloud computing technology is boom for information centres or libraries, it is offering different kinds of opportunities to reach and provide library services by cloud of information (Kadbe & Dange, 2015).

Cloud computing is web based technology, information is shared, applications are provided, and other computing devices are provided on demand with using web technology in cloud computing (Wagde, 2015).

Using Google Gmail, photos organizing on Flickr and web searching with Bing are engaged in cloud computing technology (Gaikwad, 2015).

Manipulating, configuring and online application accessing refers in cloud computing. Cloud computing offers data storage online, application and infrastructure (Tutorialspoint.com, n.d.).

Cloud computing is versatile technology, it helps in broader spectrum of applications and particularly in developing world and cloud computing is rendering on low cost in dynamic scale. It is most cost effective in innovation driven small companies (Srinivas, Reddy, & Qyser, 2012).

1.3 Objectives of the study:

- To review the concept of cloud computing.
- To explore importance of cloud computing for information atmanirbhar Bharat.
- To know the application of cloud computing in information centres / libraries.

1.4 Scope and Limitation of the study:-The study helps information and library professionals for understanding cloud computing concept and use of it for making information atmanirbhar Bharat.

1.5 Statement of the Research Problems:-Cloud computing technology has brought tremendous revolution in the information industry. Hence the study is focused on information atmanirbhar Bharat with using cloud computing technology.

1.6 Methodology:-The paper is described the cloud computing technology for making information atmanirbhar Bharat with the help of available literature in books, journals, conference proceedings and internet.

1.7 Cloud Computing:-National Institute of Technology (NIST) defined “Cloud computing is a model for enabling the network access in ubiquitous and convenient on demand to share a pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimum management effort or service provider interaction.(Jim, n.d.) It is typically defined as a type of computing that relies on sharing computing resources rather than having local server or personal devices to handle applications” (Kadbe & Dange, 2015).

Cloud is a term used as analogous to internet. Cloud computing is an internet based technology that provides virtual shared servers, software, devices, infrastructure, platform, other resources for making available on users interest on pay (LuitInfotech, n.d).

Simply cloud computing is sharing of resources and applications on internet to get work without concern about ownership and network management of resources and applications.

1.7.1 Types of Cloud Computing:

a) Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS):-Infrastructure as a Service provides virtual computers, virtual infrastructure and storage, hardware accessories etc. In this type of cloud computing, host manages the entire infrastructure. Clients are also responsible for all other deployment. This kind of cloud computing makes ideal for small and medium size organizations in a least cost and as IT solutions. Infrastructure as a service is available on fully out sourced on pay for use service. It is available in public, private and hybrid model of cloud computing.(What are the types of cloud computing?, 2021)(Patil & Patil, 2015). Example of this service is Amazon’s web services.

b) Software as a Service (SaaS):-Resources and applications are provided by host to the subscribers. Software as a service provides hardware, operating systems and other special software to the user through internet. It provides same software on all user devices for accessing it on the cloud. There is no need worry by user of the cloud about application servers, storage and related content of the information technology. Providers of SaaS Cloud are Google App, AQLAzure etc.(Gaikwad, 2015).

c) Platform as a Service (PaaS):-Host of the Platform as a service provides the access components to the subscribers which applications they require to develop and operate over the internet. This service save the cost of licence, infrastructure, reduces on going operational cost for development, test and hosting environment. This kind of cloud computing service is provided

by such vendors that Microsoft, Google, Windows Azure, Google App Engine etc. (Patil & Patil, 2015).

1.7.2 Application of Cloud Computing Technology in Information Centres or Libraries:

- i. Cloud computing technology is used for hosting website of information centres or libraries. Amazon's Elastic Computing Cloud (EC2) service is used by Columbia Public Library for hosting website. It provides services rapidly, scalability and redundancy.
- ii. Information centres can build digital library, institutional repository, content management system, and integrated library system.
- iii. Google docs is used to store library's documents and can provide to user. It is used for collect google forms, googlecalendar and google analytics to collect statistics about library website, blogs and catalogues.
- iv. Data backup is stored in cloud computing technology such bibliographical data, reports, media collections etc.

1.7.3 Cloud Computing Technology initiatives in information centres:

- Open Source Software- Koha, D-space, and Greenstone etc.
- Drupal for Content Management
- Moodle for LMS
- OCLC Webscale
- Ex-libris cloud
- Duraspace's Duracloud – Repository solutions like D-space (Kadbe & Dange, 2015).

1.7.4 Benefits of Cloud Computing in Information Centres or Libraries:

- i. Cloud Computing provides all infrastructural facilities in least cost.
- ii. Enables user to use personalized workspace.
- iii. Provides storage, backup and recovery facility.
- iv. It provides virtualized technology so virtualized services can be provided by information centres.
- v. Create user friendly environment.
- vi. It is cost effective and highly automated technology for information centres.

1.8 Conclusion:-The review of the study is that Indian Information Centres are not fully adopted cloud computing technology in the information environment. But some of Institutions like IIT Delhi are adopted and encouraging other institutions for adopting cloud computing technology for fulfilling user's requirement. The study observed that cloud computing technology gives most reliable and rapid information to the user and create paper less society. Over all study review that cloud computing technology helps India to become Information Atmanirbhar and it is the requirement of the present age of information centres or libraries.

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